

Kombucha Tea with Butterfly Pea Flower (*Clitoria Ternatea L.*) and Lemongrass Extract (*Cymbopogon Nardus L.*) as an Oral Antibacterial and Mouth Odor Eliminator

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Abstract

*Oral health in Indonesia remains a significant concern, with 57.6% of the population experiencing oral health issues according to Riskesdas 2018. Oral health is vital for overall well-being, as problems like cavities and swollen gums can interfere with daily activities. This study aims to develop a non-alcoholic mouthwash formula using natural ingredients, specifically kombucha made from Butterfly Pea flower tea (*Clitoria Ternatea L.*) and lemongrass extract (*Cymbopogon nardus L.*). This experimental study aims to develop an oral antibacterial kombucha using Butterfly Pea flower (*Clitoria Ternatea L.*) and lemongrass extract (*Cymbopogon nardus L.*). The process involves making kombucha from boiled dried Butterfly Pea flowers and preparing lemongrass extract from fresh leaves through maceration. The mixture is then tested to determine the most effective concentration for antibacterial properties. Kombucha of Butterfly Pea flower tea effectively inhibits the growth of *Streptococcus mutans* bacteria, which can cause dental and oral infections. This kombucha produced an inhibition zone of 18.67 mm, which is categorized as strong. The combination of Butterfly Pea flower tea kombucha and lemongrass showed a stronger antibacterial effect than the use of single ingredients. This product has good potential as due to its antibacterial properties, it can help reduce bacterial overgrowth that can cause dental and gum health problems. The risk of bad breath and dental problems caused by bacteria.*

Keywords: *mouthwash, butterfly pea flower, lemongrass, oral cavity, kombucha*

INTRODUCTION

Dental and oral health status has not yet received significant attention in Indonesia, as evidenced by people who tend not to feel pain in their teeth and mouth and do not take any action regarding the diseases they experience.¹ The prevalence of dental and oral problems in Indonesia, according to the 2018 Riskesdas report, is 57.6%, with a National Decay Missing Filled-Teeth (DMF-T) index of 7.1.5.² Dental and oral health is an essential part of overall human body health. This is because dental and oral health can affect overall body health, such as

missing teeth that are not replaced can lead to eating disorders, and swollen gums can interfere with daily human activities.¹

A common factor that causes dental and oral diseases is a thin layer called dental plaque. Plaque is a sticky layer that consists of bacteria. This plaque converts carbohydrates or sugars from your food into acids strong enough to damage the teeth.³ Bacteria commonly found in the oral cavity include *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus mutans*, *Streptococcus viridans*, and *Staphylococcus pneumonia*. The growth of these bacteria can cause dental

and oral health problems such as cavities, bad breath, swollen gums, and many more.

Mouthwash is often a solution for dealing with dental and oral cavity problems due to its ease of use and effective function. However, the long-term use of alcohol-based mouthwash can cause dry mouth, reduce saliva production, affect bad breath, and increase the risk of tooth decay.³

An alternative to replacing harmful substances in mouthwash is to create a new formula using natural ingredients that can prevent the growth of oral cavity bacteria and bad breath, which can threaten dental and oral health. One such natural-based mouthwash formulation is made from butterfly pea kombucha tea and lemongrass extract. Butterfly pea tea is known for its various health benefits, one of which is its high flavonoid content. The processing of butterfly pea tea into kombucha is one way to enhance the benefits of butterfly pea tea.⁴ Lemongrass is also an easily accessible medicinal plant with many health benefits, including inhibiting bacterial growth.⁵ Based on these facts, this study on the formulation of butterfly pea kombucha tea and lemongrass extract is expected to provide a herbal and alcohol-free mouthwash alternative for the community.

METHOD

The preparation of butterfly pea tea will be done by drying the butterfly pea flowers until they are completely dry, then boiling the dried flowers and using the boiled extract for product production. The flow of the research is showed in figure 1.

Figure 1. Research flow

The fermentation stage uses sugar as the main substrate and the initial kombucha culture with baby scoby in liquid kombucha form. Butterfly pea tea is weighed to 17.2% in 1 liter of water. The water is measured to 7.2% until the remaining 2.4% moisture content is suitable for the butterfly pea flowers. Then, sugar is added according to the treatment concentrations, which are 20%, 30%, and 40%, and the mixture is poured into glass bottles. The next step involves pouring the boiling butterfly pea tea into jars that have had the respective sugar concentrations added, cooling the mixture to 25°C, adding the kombucha starter, and allowing the fermentation process to proceed statically at room temperature for 12 days.⁶ A phytochemical test will be conducted on the kombucha to identify flavonoid content, as this substance is sought for its antibacterial properties. The antibacterial test will be conducted by cultivating *Streptococcus*

mutans and *Staphylococcus aureus* on agar media using the disk diffusion method. Chlorhexidine gluconate will be used as the positive control, and distilled water will be used as the negative control.

The part of the lemongrass plant used is the fresh lemongrass leaves. The lemongrass leaves are thoroughly washed with running water, cut, and then drained. The lemongrass leaves are then blended, squeezed, and filtered. A phytochemical test will be conducted on the lemongrass extract to identify the presence of terpenoids. The extracted juice will be prepared in four different concentrations: 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50%. These four concentrations will be tested on bacterial colonies, and the diameter of the inhibition zones for each concentration will be measured. The antibacterial test will be conducted by cultivating *Streptococcus mutans* and *Staphylococcus aureus* on agar media. Chlorhexidine gluconate will be used as the positive control, and distilled water will be used as the negative control.⁸

The mixing process will be carried out after the completion of making butterfly pea tea, butterfly pea kombucha, and lemongrass extract. The mixing process will use different product concentrations, and the most effective result will be selected.

RESULT

The preparation of butterfly pea tea begins with picking fresh butterfly pea flowers. The flowers are cut from the stem using a sterile knife to avoid contamination. After being picked, the butterfly pea flowers are dried in an oven at 60°C for 24 hours. The dried flowers are then ground using a blender to make the brewing process easier. The ground

butterfly pea flowers are then brewed by placing the ground flowers into hot water at 80°C. After brewing, the butterfly pea tea is filtered using a sieve to remove the residue, resulting in a clearer tea.

The preparation of kombucha begins by purchasing a baby scoby, which is then cultivated by mixing it with 1 liter of butterfly pea tea at 45°C. The mixture is then combined with 100 grams of sugar. The next step is to let the mixture sit until the bacteria and yeast become active, producing kombucha. The finished kombucha is then filtered using a sieve to remove any scoby residue, resulting in clear kombucha. The filtered kombucha is then bottled in tightly sealed containers and stored at room temperature.

The preparation of lemongrass extract begins by selecting 1 kilogram of high-quality lemongrass. The selected lemongrass is then washed under running water to clean it of dirt. After washing, the lemongrass is cut into small pieces, 3-4 cm in size. The lemongrass pieces are then weighed to 200 grams and placed in a separate container. The lemongrass is then dried in an oven at 60°C for 24 hours.

After drying, the lemongrass pieces are ground using a blender to facilitate the maceration process, producing 200 grams of powder. The lemongrass is then macerated with 1 liter of 96% ethanol for 24 hours. Research results showed that a combination of kombucha with butterfly pea tea and 100 grams of sugar is effective in inhibiting the growth of *Streptococcus mutans*, which can cause dental and oral infections. The inhibition zone produced with 100 grams of sugar was 18.67 mm, categorized as strong.

The combination of butterfly pea kombucha and lemongrass showed stronger antibacterial effects compared to using single ingredients.

DISCUSSION

The preparation of butterfly pea tea begins with picking fresh butterfly pea flowers, drying, grinding, and brewing the flowers with hot water. A filtration process is conducted to produce clear butterfly pea tea, ready to serve.

Kombucha is made by cultivating a baby scoby in a mixture of butterfly pea tea, sugar, and fermenting it to produce a probiotic drink. After the fermentation process is complete, the kombucha is filtered to produce a clear drink and stored in tightly sealed bottles.

Lemongrass extract is made by selecting, washing, drying, and grinding lemongrass. A maceration process with 96% ethanol is conducted to produce an extract that is ready for use. Research shows that the combination of kombucha with butterfly pea tea is effective in inhibiting the growth of *Streptococcus mutans*, with 100 grams of sugar providing a strong inhibition effect.

CONCLUSION

This product has good potential as a breath freshener due to its ability to eliminate unpleasant odors in the oral cavity. Additionally, with its antibacterial properties, this product can help reduce the overgrowth of bacteria that can cause dental and gum health issues. With the combination of these two benefits, the product can be an effective choice for maintaining oral health and

reducing the risk of bad breath and dental health problems caused by bacteria.

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